

STUDY OF THE LEVEL OF FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS IN CHILDREN 6-7 YEARS OLD WITH MENTAL DEVELOPMENT RETARDATION

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Abstract. *It is important to suggest that according to the UN World Health Organization, people with disabilities make up about 15 percent of the world's population, and the regular increase in this indicator makes it necessary to consider as a priority the task of creating opportunities for everyone to feel equal to others and realize their potential. Children with mental retardation make up a large percentage in kindergartens and schools. The importance of assessing special educational needs and psychological and pedagogical support in general educational institutions, taking into account their psychophysical and educational needs, is a paramount task for the entire peaceful community. In the Republic of Kazakhstan, in recent years, a regulatory framework has been created for improving special education, raising a comprehensively developed young generation, high-quality preparation of children for school education, preparing children with various speech disorders for school education, their intellectual, speech, spiritual, aesthetic, and physical development.*

Keywords: *defectologists, inclusive education, secondary school, monitor, spiritual development.*

The following tasks have been identified as priorities: “Creating conditions for inclusive education in secondary schools, developing criteria for determining the quality and effectiveness of inclusive education, as well as monitoring their implementation; conducting scientific research, studying and applying in practice the best foreign experience of inclusive education”. The priority objectives are: “Providing children with special educational needs with accessible and high-quality education, as well as their receipt of a full-fledged education at all stages, creating conditions for the development of inclusive education. As a result, ample opportunities are created for the intellectual and physical development of children with special educational needs, the continuous implementation of inclusive education, and the improvement of regulatory and methodological foundations in the context of special and inclusive education.

Particularly, the research will be carried out in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On social and medical-pedagogical correctional support for children with disabilities", which establishes the basic principles and mechanisms for providing assistance to such children. The provisions of the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Education" with additions will also be taken into account, The Law “On the Rights of the Child in the Republic of Kazakhstan”, the Law “On Social Protection of Persons with Disabilities in the Republic of Kazakhstan” and the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated January 8, 2021 N. 410-VI MDR, introducing changes and additions to some legislative acts of the Republic of Kazakhstan on education issues.

In addition, the study will take into account the Order of the Minister of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan N. 4 dated January 12, which approves the “Rules of

psychological and pedagogical support in educational organizations” as well as the Order of the Minister of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan N. 6 dated January 12, 2022, where the “Model rules for the activities of special educational organizations” are regulated. Recommendations for organizing integrated (inclusive) education for children with developmental disabilities, contained in the letter of the Ministry of Education and Science dated March 16, 2009 N. 4-02-4/450, as well as “Methodological recommendations for identifying children with autism in educational organizations” will also be taken into account, specified in letter of the Ministry of Education and Science N. 4-02-4/1435, dated May 28, 2010.

In the Republic of Kazakhstan, research in the field of development of special education, improvement of the inclusive education system and improvement of methods of working with children with special educational needs was carried out by scientists Omirbekova K.K., Suleimenova R.A., Movkebaeva Z.A., Abaeva G.A., Autaeva A.N., Eliseeva I.G., Denisova I.A., Baitursynova A.A., Ersarina A.K., Orazbaeva G.S., Adilova M.Sh., Baybekova M.M., Sembaeva A.M., Kalykbaeva A.Zh., Omirbekova S.Zh., Satova A.M., Kasen G.A. and Tuganbekova K.M. as well, where the issues are considered that independently, without targeted training, communicative activity in these children develops with a significant lag behind the communication skills and skills of normally developing peers. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, issues of education and training of children with intellectual disabilities are reflected in the scientific works of such teachers as Aitmetova S.Sh., Kim S.G., Muminova L.R., Rakhmanova V.S., Shomakhmudova R., Gordienko D. A.A., Sadikova G.A., Khamidova M.P., Nurkeldieva D.A., Nurmukhammedova L.Sh., Amirsaidova Sh.M., Pulatova P.M., Sosedova N.V., Sagatov et al. Scientists from the CIS countries, in particular Russia M.S. Pevzner, V.I. Lubovsky, T.A. Vlasova. K.S. Lebedinskaya, U.V. Ulienkova, E.E. Dmitrieva, E.N. Vasilyeva, M.I. Gumenyuk, E.A. Chernysheva, D.I. Boykov, S.G. Shevchenko, D.R. Bulgakova, that “Insufficient development of communication skills in children with mental retardation is a significant medical and social problem, the solution of which not only psychologists and teachers, but also child psychiatrists. Assistance in overcoming the communication barrier for children with mental retardation should be carried out both at the family level and at the level of society as a whole. Parents must know and take into account the peculiarities of the mental development of their children and use adequate parenting styles.

Certainly, society, for its part should show tolerance towards children with developmental disabilities, be informed and prepared for inclusive education. Allocation of funds and opportunities in preschool and school educational institutions to organize the communication process of children with mental retardation also seems necessary to solve the problem of the formation and development of communication skills of children with mental retardation.” Foreign researchers: R. Payne (1968), A. Strauss (1947) define mental retardation as minimal brain dysfunction (MBD). However, minimal brain dysfunction is a neurological concept and definition. The consequences of this dysfunction can lead to signs of delayed mental development. The duration of this disease mainly depends on early intervention, timeliness and adequacy of the use of special methods and special training techniques. Foreign researchers such as Dr. Marion Blank, Dr. Rhea Paul, Judith Johnston, Dr. Gina Conti-Ramsden, Dr. Gretchen Hannigan studied the development of communication skills in children with special needs and is researching the effectiveness of such techniques and identifying factors that influence communicative development in children with mental retardation.

Definitely, developed and created through the efforts of defectologists from Kazakhstan, the system of special practical assistance to children with mental retardation has achieved significant success. But, however, scientific research on this problem is not enough, since in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan the need for further research to improve diagnostics, develop effective methods of support and create individual correction programs determined the relevance of our research.

It is not a secret that the current period issues of organizing speech therapy work with children with mental retardation in Kazakhstan are associated with the insufficient availability of speech therapy assistance. Lack of qualified speech therapists in the regions, especially in rural areas, limited number of specialized institutions for children with mental retardation, difficulties in obtaining referrals for speech therapy classes, insufficient integration of speech therapy work into the general educational system, lack of uniform standards and training programs for speech therapists adapted for children with mental retardation, insufficient interaction between speech therapists and teachers in educational institutions, lack of materials and methods for teaching children 6-7 years old with mental retardation.

Undeniably, problems with early diagnosis and early help, insufficient awareness of parents about mental retardation and the need for timely speech therapy assistance, lack of specialists in early child development centers capable of diagnosing mental retardation at an early stage, lack of an integrated approach to correction, limitation of speech therapy work only to speech correction, without taking into account others developmental problems associated with mental retardation, lack of close interaction with other specialists working with children with mental retardation (psychologists, teachers, neuropsychologists), insufficient opportunities for professional development of speech therapists, limited access to modern methods and technologies of speech therapy correction, lack of opportunities for advanced training and professional growth.

It should be suggested that based on the relevance of the problem, the purpose of the study was to determine the content of correctional work on the development of communication skills in children 6-7 years old with mental retardation in the general education system. It can be believed that the difficulties in communicating with other people in children 6-7 years old with mental retardation are associated with the inadequacy of forms of communication, the underdevelopment of its structural components, the slowdown and qualitative originality of emotional, personal, mental development; overcoming these difficulties is possible provided that a system of correctional measures is developed, including the targeted development of communication skills in children with mental retardation. In accordance with the purpose, this article highlights one of the objectives of the study - identifying the characteristics of the state of development of communication skills in children 6-7 years old with mental retardation.

Organization and methodology of research. The basis of the study was the “Psychological-Medical-Pedagogical Consultation”, N. 6 of the Turkestan Region and secondary schools of the Turkestan Region (Sairam, Tyulkubas and Dzhetyysay districts and a school in Shymkent with the Kazakh language of instruction) of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The purpose of the ascertaining experiment is to identify the level of communication skills of children with mental retardation aged 6-7 years and to determine the current state of their communicative development. The ascertaining experiment to identify the communication skills of children with mental retardation at the age of 6-7 years included the following stages: forming a group of

children, developing a methodology, conducting an experiment, evaluating the results, formulating conclusions and recommendations.

The experiment involved 249 children of 0th and 1st grades of secondary schools in the Turkestan region: Sairam, Tyulkubas, Dzhetysay districts and the city of Shymkent.

Diagnostic methods:

1. Observation. It was observed children with mental retardation in free play in the classroom (interaction with other children, use of speech, non-verbal signals), in situational games (dramatization, solving problem situations, completing tasks in pairs), in lessons (participation in dialogue, expression your opinion, understanding the instructions).

2. Conversation: in a conversation on a given topic (understanding questions, constructing a coherent answer, using detailed phrases), aimed at testing the understanding of sentences, the ability to express one’s feelings and thoughts.

3. Testing: “Pictogram” test: assessment of understanding of non-verbal signals (emotions, actions). Test "Pictures in order": assessment of understanding of the sequence of events, logic, story. Test "Repeat sentences": assessment of speech memory, understanding of grammatical structures. Test "Complete the sentence": assessment of vocabulary, understanding of synonyms and antonyms.

For evaluating the results of the study, there was developed criteria and indicators for the level of development of communication skills in children 6-7 years old with mental retardation (Table N. 1)

Criteria and indicators of the level of development of communication skills

Table-1

Criteria (points)	Parameters
Low (1 points)	significant difficulties in communication, the child finds it difficult to establish contact with others, does not use verbal and non-verbal means of communication, does not understand simple instructions, and cannot conduct a dialogue. The first level of speech development (according to R.E. Levin)
Average (2 points)	some problems in communication, the child can make contact, use simple verbal and non-verbal means of communication, understands simple instructions, can conduct a short dialogue. Second level of speech development (according to R.E. Levin)
High (3 points)	there are no significant difficulties with communication, the child easily makes contact, uses a variety of verbal and non-verbal means of communication, understands complex instructions, can conduct everyday dialogue, and takes into account the interests of other people. The third level of speech development (according to R.E. Levin)

As can be seen from Table N. 2, the indicators of the levels of development of all communication skills (initiative, establishing contact, verbal communication, non-verbal communication, adherence to communication rules, interaction with other children) are at a low

level of 61 children (25%), with an average level of 183 children (73.4%), with a high level of 5 children (2%). As the results of the experiment showed, communication skills are characterized by the fact that among the tested children with mental retardation 6-7 years old, the following errors were often noted: lack of concentration in actions, reduced speed and level of assimilation of information, difficulties in solving problems, logical thinking, limited vocabulary, difficulties with understanding of abstract concepts, unclear articulation, defects in sound pronunciation, difficulties in understanding and using grammatical structures, limited vocabulary, problems with constructing sentences, difficulties in understanding non-verbal cues such as gestures, facial expressions, difficulties in establishing and maintaining social contacts, problems with comprehension social norms and rules, a limited circle of interests and friends, difficulties with concentration, memory, spatial thinking, reduced cognitive activity, increased anxiety, self-doubt, low self-esteem, problems with self-control, a tendency to impulsive actions.

№	Criteria	Low level	Average	High level
		(1 point)	level (2 points)	(3 points)
	Communicative skills			
1	Initiativeness	66 (26,5%)	180 (72,2%)	3 (1,2%)
2	Establishing contact	56 (22,4%)	189 (75,9%)	4 (1,6%)
3	Speech skills	39 (15,6%)	197 (79,1%)	13 (5,2%)
4	Non-verbal communication	67 (26,9%)	180 (72,2%)	2 (0,8%)
5	Following communication rules	68 (27,3%)	173 (69,4%)	8 (3,2%)
6	Interaction with other children	72 (28,9%)	173 (69,4%)	4 (1,6%)
	Total number of children on all categories	61	183	5
	Percentage	25%	73,4%	2%

Conclusion. While studying, there was examined 249 children aged 6-7 years with mental retardation. At the ascertaining stage of the experiment, the following features of the indicators of children with mental and speech retardation were obtained. The development of communication skills (initiative, establishing contact, verbal communication, adherence to communication rules, interaction with other children) amounted to:

- with a low level of 61 children (25%), children do not make contact and show negativism.
- with an average level of 183 children (73.4%), they do not make contact immediately, do not fully understand the addressed speech, and give monosyllabic answers.
- with a high level of 5 children (2%), these children easily come into contact with adults, understand basic speech, know how to listen, know how to answer questions, but the answers are not always detailed. Communication becomes socially significant. The child learns to interact in a group and takes into account the interests of other children.

The results of the study showed that children 6-7 years old with mental retardation have a reduced need for communication. The formation of communication with “strangers” in most children with mental retardation is at the situational and business level inherent in normatively developing children of an earlier age. Children with mental retardation have difficulties in developing communication skills. The imperfection of the communicative sphere does not ensure

the process of communication, and therefore does not contribute to the development of cognitive activity. Communication of children with mental retardation, in contrast to their normatively developing peers, is characterized by a low level of speech activity; their common basis is the immaturity of the motivational-need sphere. Communication of children with mental retardation with adults is at a lower level of development than that of their normally developing peers. The communication of children with mental retardation with each other also differs in a number of features from the communication of their normally developing peers. Communication with peers in children with mental retardation is episodic. Most children prefer to play alone. In cases where children play together, their actions are often uncoordinated. The role-playing play of children with mental retardation can be defined more as a game “side by side” than as a joint activity. Communication regarding the game is observed in isolated cases.

Definitely, the experimental data obtained during the study not only showed a significant lag behind age norms in the development of communication in children aged 6-7 years with mental retardation, but also made it possible to identify the qualitative uniqueness of the formation of their communicative activity. Therefore, the results obtained indicate that the purposeful formation of children’s communicative activity and the achievement of its developmental effect becomes possible while creating developmental educational conditions in the system of special education and training. One of the forms of these conditions can be systematic, regulated, specially organized communicative training during play activities, which will provide the child with the opportunity to correctly interact with the people around him in various situations.

In conclusion, it can be suggested that comparing the results of examination of children 6-7 years old, there can be stated that the level of development of communication skills of children with mental retardation is above the average level of development. Thanks to the data obtained, the need for correctional work with children 6-7 years old with mental retardation was identified.

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